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Digital Payment Instruments and Liquidity of Nigeria Financial Market

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the effect of digital payment instruments and liquidity of Nigeria economy using time series data from 2009 to 2023. Data were sourced from Central Bank of Nigeria Statistical Bulletin. Liquidity of the economy was model as the function of automated teller machine, point of sale, electronic fund transfer, mobile payment and e-wallet. Autoregressive distribution lag square was used as data analysis methods. R-square, adjusted R-square, Durbin Watson, probability value, regression coefficient, F-statistic and probability was used to analyze the relationship between the dependent variable (liquidity of Nigeria economy) and the independent variables (digital payment instruments). The study found that 91.7 percent of the variance in liquidity of Nigeria economy was explained by changes in digital payment instruments. The F-statistic for the regression model is 28.30617, and the P-value is 0.000000, which indicates that the model fits the data well overall. The Durbin Watson Statistic was calculated to be 2.033353 which suggested that there were some degree of temporal dependency in the level series, which might lead to erroneous regression findings. The study found that automated teller machine, point of sales, electronic fund transfer have negative effect on liquidity of the economy while e-wallet and mobile payment have positive effect on the liquidity of the economy. From the findings we concluded that digital payment instruments have significant effect on the liquidity of Nigeria economy. We recommended that Central Bank of Nigeria should ensure quantity of money supply that correspond with various digital payment instruments and the liquidity of the economy. Public awareness should be advanced on the effect of digital payment instruments on the liquidity of the economy.

Keywords: Digital Payment Instruments, Liquidity, Nigeria Economy

INTRODUCTION

In the 21st Century, new financial regulation and innovation shift activities across different financial institutes, the landscape of the financial industry is constantly changing. One of the most important innovations is the Internet money market funds launched by mutual fund companies and digital payment platforms. Compared with traditional money market funds, the money invested in Internet money market funds can be directly used for payment, transfer and repayment with a third-party payment platform, which meets the user's demand for one-stop financial management and consumption (Baiyere, Salmela & Tapanainen, 2020). Leveraging the openness feature of digital payment platforms, Internet money market funds have attracted multiple times more inflows compared to traditional money market funds. Although

the returns of Internet money market funds are lower than traditional MMFs most of the time, they still maintain rapid growth. In recent years, with the interest rate declining, the return of Internet MMFs has continued to decline, while the total assets of these funds have not seen a significant drop.

Historically, the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) introduced a payment system which facilitated e-payment in 2002. During this period, Nigeria's Automated Clearing System (NACS) was introduced as a veritable platform for the development of electronic payment and to reduce the clearing of cheques period. Shortly after was the introduction of the Automated Teller Machine (ATM), web pay channels, Point of Sales and mobile payment channels, just to mention a few. Electronic payment systems come in different forms; some of the e-payment systems related to this study are Point of Sales, web pay channels and mobile payment channels.

Financial market liquidity typically implies that investors can conduct a large number of financial market transactions in a brief time frame without experiencing significant price volatility. Financial market with higher liquidity has smaller immediate trading losses and lower investment risk. As the lifeline of the capital market, stock liquidity is one of the important core contents of the stock market (Amihud & Mendelson, 1998). It fulfills the functions of price discovery, information flow, and resource optimization while also reflecting the significance of corporate behavior in the capital market recognition. The liquidity of financial market not only has an impact on investor confidence and the value of the stock market, but it also influences the capital market activities of corporations, the effective allocation of market resources, and the stable development of the real economy. In recent years, relevant academic research has focused on the influencing factors and direct economic consequences of the digital payment mechanism. In the digital economy, digital technologies, such as artificial intelligence, blockchain, cloud computing, and big data, have rapidly advanced, and digitalization has gradually become a significant breakthrough in restructuring production factors, reshaping economic structures, and transforming competition patterns in economic development. According to studies, companies can improve their business processes and models enhance organizational management and promote innovation, and increase enterprise value creation and acquisition with digital payment instruments (Zhang, Ye, Wei, Kashif, & Cao 2023).

Moreover, various levels of digital transformation such as the payment instrument can improve market competitiveness and sustainable development capabilities by expanding the density of digital technology and improving the depth and breadth of digital technology application. At the same time, enterprises represent the micro-foundation of the capital market. The digital payment impact the functioning of the financial market, including price discovery, market policy transmission, information transmission, expectation management, risk mitigation, and other related aspects (An & Rau, 2021). Transformative and innovative digital payment behaviors and the resulting improvements in operational efficiency and economic performance have overwhelming advantages in the financial market offering a wealth of information for the adjustment of financial market resource allocation, but they also present challenges to corporate governance (An, Ding & Lin, 2023). From a theoretical perspective, in the context of the digital economy, improving corporate governance is an important way to accelerate corporate transformation and upgrading and enhance corporate sustainable development capabilities. The digital payment instrument provide new momentum to the production business process, influence the organizational governance structure, resource allocation efficiency, and information disclosure system, and propel corporate governance efficiency and quality, thus affecting liquidity in the economy.

Studies has verified the impact of digital payment instruments on the financial market from different perspectives, such as the ability of enterprise digital transformation to improve the capital market environment inhibit the risk of stock price crash and reduce stock price volatility (Chen, Zhang, Jiang, Meng & Sun, 2022; Ai, Sun, & Kong, 2022). The external capital market effects of enterprise digital transformation have yet to be fully explored, particularly in terms of in-depth mechanism analysis, which is primarily manifested in the important capital market factor of stock liquidity. Furthermore, studies financial market liquidity from the perspectives of market uncertainty, monetary policy, asset liquidity, financing constraints, corporate governance and information disclosure among other perspectives. Digital payment instruments as a radical change factor also have an impact on the liquidity of the financial

market which has long been neglected by previous researchers (Gopalan, Kadan, Pevzner, 2022; Quah, Haman & Naidu, 2021; Prommin, Jumreornvong, & Jiraporn, 2014; Schoenfeld 2017; Bennett, Stulz & Wang, 2020). Hence, the research findings of this study contributed to the enrichment of the discussion regarding the effect of digital payment instruments on the liquidity of the emerging financial market like Nigeria.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Digital Payment Instruments

Digital Payment Instruments (e-payment systems) refer to the automated processes of exchanging monetary value among parties in business transactions and transmitting this value over the ICT networks (Amin & Osuagwu, 2018). In Nigeria, e-payment is effecting payment from one end to another end through the medium of the computer without manual intervention beyond inputting payment data. It is the ability to pay the suppliers, vendors and staff salaries electronically at the touch of a computer button (Udeghi & Hanzace, 2018). In the wake of the cashless policy, the e-payment system has become a medium through which monetary substance circulates conveniently, especially in a developing economy like Nigeria where carrying cash around is habitual. In Nigeria, the e-payment system formed the fundamental starting point of her modern market economy; a well-functioning e-payment system has been recognized to have much relevance on financial stability, monetary policy and overall economic activity (Aduda & Kingoo, 2018). Digital payment is electronic payment as a form of financial exchange that takes place between the buyer and seller facilitated by means of electronic communication. According to Cobb (2004), the value of electronic payment goes way beyond the immediate convenience and safety of cards to a greater sphere of contributing to overall economic development. The term electronic payment can be referred narrowly to e-commerce- a payment for buying and selling goods and services offered through the internet, or broadly to any type of electronic funds transfer (Massimo & Garcia, 2008). Ayodele (2007) defined e-payment as electronic transfer of cash via online transactions for business-to-business (B2B), business-to-consumer (B2C), person-to-person (P2P), and most recently administration-to-consumer (A2C) purposes. A2C payment addresses the payment of taxes toward the government. Payments are part of our individual daily lives, electronic payments when transacting business on the streets, in stores, online, using different payment technologies. For the most part of the 1900s, cash and cheques were the most common means of transacting business among individuals and between organizations (Evans & Schmalensee, 2005).

Payment cards like credit and debit cards were introduced in the second half of the 1900s for store purchases and eventually to make cash withdrawals from Automatic Teller Machines (ATMs) (Slawsky & Zafar, 2005). Towards the end of the 1990s, electronic commerce was viewed as an alternative way of conducting financial transactions over the Internet which subsequently led to internet payments (Zwass, 1996) and the merger between the internet and banks (Sandén, 1998). The recent introduction of mobile payment applications adds to the variety of digital payment technologies (Chae & Hedman, 2015). In our society today, customers are not only charged with the responsibility of choosing between goods and services but also between payment technology options. An example is, even with online payment, the customer will choose between internet bank transfer, the use of POS terminals or even PayPal.

Humphrey, Kim and Vale (2001) defined e-payment as cash and associated transactions implemented using electronic means. Typically, this involves the use of computer networks such as the internet and digital stored value system. This system allows bills to be paid directly from bank, and without the use of writing and mailing cheques. Guttman (2003) defined e-payment as credit card details, or some other electronic means, as opposed to payment by cheque and cash. It is also defined as a payer's transfer of monetary claim on a party acceptable to the beneficiary (Worku 2010). Electronic payment can also be defined as convenient, safe and secure methods for payment of bills and other transactions by electronic means such as card, telephone, the internet, EFT and etc. Electronic payment gives consumers an alternative to paying bills and debts by cash, cheque, money order etc. Its main purpose is to reduce cash and cheque transactions. In the Nigeria context, e-payment is effecting payments from one end to another

and through the medium of the computer without manual intervention beyond inputting the payment data; it is the ability to pay the suppliers, vendors and staff salaries electronically at the touch of a computer button (Agba, 2010).

Tadesse and Kidan (2005) observed that there is a correlation between increase in point of sales volumes and rise in demand deposits. Automated electronic payments act as a gateway into the banking sector and as a powerful engine for growth. Such payments draw cash out of circulation and into the bank accounts, providing low cost funds that can be used to support bank lending for investment- a driver of overall economic activity. The process creates greater transparency and accountability, leading to greater efficiency and better economic performance. Electronic payment is very convenient for the consumer. In most cases, you only need to enter your account information- such as your credit card number and shipping address- once. The information is then stored in a database on the retailer's web server. When you come back to the website, you just log in with your username and password. Completing a transaction is as simple as clicking your mouse: All you have to do is confirm your purchase and you are done.

Worku (2010) emphasized the fact that electronic payment lowers costs for businesses. The more payments that is processed electronically, the less money is spent on paper and postage. Offering electronic payment can also help businesses improve customer retention. "A customer is more likely to return to the e-commerce site where his or her information has already been entered and stored". According to Tadesse and Kidan (2005) electronic payments can thus lower transaction costs stimulate higher consumption and GDP, increase government efficiency boost financial intermediation and improve financial transparency". They further added that "Governments play a critically important role in creating an environment in which these benefits can be achieved in a way consistent with their own economic development plans". The introduction and use of electronic payment instruments holds the promise of broad benefit to both business and consumers in the form of reduced, greater convenience and more secure reliable means of payment and settlement for a potentially vast range of goods and services offered worldwide over the internet or other electronic networks. One such benefit is that electronic payments enable bank customers to handle their daily financial transactions without having to visit their local bank branch. Electronic payments products could save merchants time and expense in handling cash (Appiah & Agyemang, 2007).

The use of internet is also increasing the global importance of the services industry in international trade market. There are various types of electronic payment (e-payment) system practiced around the world presently. However, the following are most pronounced.

i). Electronic Funds Transfer (EFT): This is a means of transferring money electronically by banks and other financial institutions. Shukla (2017) explained the term as *electronic transfer* of money from one bank account to another, either within a single financial institution or across multiple institutions, via computer-based systems, without the direct intervention of bank staff. To Ayodele (2015), electronic funds transfer provides an easy, cheaper and faster method of transferring money. It helps individuals and organizations to save on costs such as printing checks as well as the time to deliver or collect checks and deposit them in the banks for processing. Just like Payroll Direct Deposit and ATM transactions, EFT payments are extremely safe. All payment information is encrypted with 128-bit secure sockets layer (SSL) and sent through a secure communications channel. Information cannot be redirected, read, or tampered with (Ejoh, Adebisi & Okpa, 2014). The following are the major instruments for the transfer.

ii). Payment Cards (PCs): These cards contain stored financial value that can be transferred from the customer's computer to the businessman's computer.

iii). Credit Cards (CCs): These are the most popular method of payment used in the electronic payment system (EPSs) and are used by charging customer's credits.

iv). Smart Cards (SCs): These cards contain vital financial and personal information of the owner stored for online transactions.

v). Electronic Money (e-money/e-cash): This is standard money converted into an electronic format using plastic encrypted card to pay for online transactions.

vi). Online Payment (OP): This is a medium of payment used to pay for services rendered monthly. Such services may include utility/bill payments and other payments that could be done online.

vii). Electronic Wallets (e-wallets): These are like smart cards. E-wallets also contain financial values which are stored for any payment that is affected online.

viii). Micro-Payment Systems (Mic-Pay): These modes of transaction are like the e-wallets. They also contain financial values which are stored for any payment that is affected online. However, as the name implies, the Mic-pay is only used to effect small transactions.

ix). Electronic Gifts (EGs): These are platforms for sending money or gifts electronically from one individual to another. The beneficiary of e-gift can spend it in their favorite online stores provided they accept this type of currency. In all of these payment systems however, the bottom line is to assure domestic and international businesses of a guaranteed payments. Also, the case for transacting customers to be assured that what they paid for electronically is received and goods or services purchased are delivered on time

Mobile Payment Channels

Mobile payment channels also known as M-banking or SMS banking are the term used for performing balance checks, account transactions, payments etc. through mobile banking products such as mobile phones (Clive, 2017). Mobile payment channels are one of the latest ways of making payments through mobile phones. This involves sending a payment request through a text message (USSD) or the bank's mobile application. Mobile payments reduce the time and stress of using a credit card or cash as account details is already linked with the banks' software (Hodagho, 2016). Mobile payment products provide basic banking services to customers from their mobile phones. It is an SMS-driven platform which facilitates access to banking services using cell phones. The services available on the mobile banking product include mini statements and checking of account history, alerts on account activity or passing of set thresholds, monitoring of term deposits, domestic and international fund transfers, micro-payment handling, bill payment processing, portfolio management services, the status of requests for credit, including mortgage approval and insurance coverage, cheque book and card requests, ATM location, general information such as weather updates, news and location-based services (Andrea et al., 2022).

Benefits of the Digital Payment Instruments

Undoubtedly, an efficient payment system (that which depends less on cash) is a sinequa-non for national development and a significant national infrastructure for growth. All things being equal, it has been shown that 10% increase in the efficiency of the national payment system can cause the Gross Domestic Product to increase by 1% (Odior & Banuso, 2012). With the advent of cash-less policy in Nigeria, Opinions on this differ

Transaction charges are seen to make significant contribution to the profits of the banks. The cash-less Nigeria programme has even brightened the horizon for the banks to make even higher income from transaction fees. Isn't this likely to result in "armchair banking whereby banks will do little to mobilize deposits and build credit asset while also scaling back retail distribution outlet as has been reported. On the other hand there are those who are optimistic about the policy. For instance, Zayyanu, Umar and Taiwo (2022) believed that if the reported two-third of the total cash in the economy which are outside the banking system is brought in (as it will be in cash-less economy), the banks will have enough resources to do their businesses. Still expressing optimism, this study agrees with the submissions of Laoye (2011), Akhalumeh and Ohiokha (2012), and Okey (2012) that if the cashless policy is successfully implemented, the following benefits will be attained.

- i. A shift towards cash-less policy will reduce the high operational cost incurred in a cash based economy. Such costs emanate from cash management and movement, currency sorting and printing.
- ii. Cash-less policy will help minimize the risks associated with the use of physical cash that do arise from burglaries and thefts as well as financial losses in fire outbreaks.
- iii. Cash-less economy will make every segment of the banking population to pay for its usage of cash. The situation in the cash based system where the majority small cash users pay for the minority high cash users will stop. There will be no more subsidies on cash transaction costs. To recapitulate, a survey

conducted by the CBN in 2009 revealed that 90% of bank customers' daily withdrawals are amounts below N150, 000, whereas, only 10% of the bank customers who withdraw over N150, 000 are responsible for the rise in cost of cash management incurred by all the customers. Implicitly, the entire banking population supports financially the costs that the minority (10%) incurs. A cashless economy will reduce this subsidy and makes the minority of the bank population account for the cost of cash movement they incur rather than the entire banking population.

iv. Cash-less economy will arrest a situation where a lot of cash are outside the formal banking system. By encouraging formal financial arrangement, it will facilitate the effectiveness of monetary policy in checking inflation and pushing economic growth.

v. Furthermore, cash-less economy is capable of reducing corrupt practices like money laundering which is common-place in cash based economy. To the extent that cash is not easily pulled out of the system, it will discourage launders.

vi. The cash-less economy will bring about increased convenience, more service option, reduced risk of cash related crimes, cheaper access to banking services, and credit to customers.

vii. Corporate organizations will benefit by way of faster access to capital, reduce revenue leakages and reduce cash handling cost.

viii. On the part of the government, it will bring about increased tax collection, greater financial inclusion, reduced revenue leakages and increase economic development.

ix. Other stakeholders: The cash-less system brings along with it different banking instruments such as POS systems, mobile payments, direct debits, internet banking, electronic fund transfer etc. Implicitly, companies that are connected with the production of these products will benefit.

Such companies include: Nigeria Inter-Bank Settlement System Plc (a shared infrastructure company of the bankers committee with a mandate to continuously enhance the Nigeria payments system owned by all licensed deposit money banks in Nigeria and the CBN), POS manufacturers, telecom providers, and switch operators.

Point of Sales

The point of sale is a location where a transaction occurs between a buyer and a seller. It is the final step in a retail transaction where the buyer pays for the goods or services purchased from the seller (Friedman & Johnson, 2019). Point of Sales (POS) terminals is a terminal that enables buyers to make payments using payment cards such as (Visa, MasterCard, verve, etc) issued to them by any bank in or outside Nigeria directly into other accounts (Osuigwe, 2022). In recent years, the POS has evolved to include electronic payment systems that make transactions faster, easier, and more secure. A POS system typically includes hardware and software components that enable the processing of sales transactions. The hardware may include a cash register, barcode scanner, card reader, receipt printer, and other peripheral devices. The software component may include a user interface, inventory management, and reporting features (Smith, 2018). One of the main advantages of a POS system is that it can reduce errors and streamline the checkout process, resulting in faster transactions and increased customer satisfaction (Maverick, 2021). POS systems can also help businesses manage their inventory, track sales data, and generate reports that can provide valuable insights into their operations (Lee, 2019)

Web Pay Channels

Web pay channels also known as internet banking are a type of e-payment system that involves transactions carried out over the Internet. Web pay channels refer to online payment gateways that enable customers to purchase goods and services from businesses or individuals through the internet (Foster, 2018). These channels allow customers to pay for their purchases electronically, without the need for cash or physical payment methods. It is a simple way of paying for online purchases directly from the customer's bank. It also offers the possibility of enjoying banking services from their homes or offices (Osang, 2017). Anyanwaokoro (2017) asserted that web pay channels are online platforms through which customers of the bank can access their accounts and accomplish financial transactions using the internet. With internet banking customers can view account balances, transfer funds between sister accounts, and transfer funds in favour of third parties. Web pay channels can be integrated into e-commerce websites,

enabling businesses to accept online payments for their products or services. Examples of popular web pay channels include PayPal, flutterpay, Alipay, and Square, which provide secure payment processing services that protect the sensitive information of customers during transactions. One significant advantage of web pay channels is that they provide convenience and ease of use for both businesses and customers. With web pay channels, customers can make purchases from anywhere at any time, as long as they have an internet connection. Businesses can also receive payments in real-time, without having to wait for checks to clear or for manual processing (Russell, 2016).

Automated Teller Machine (ATM)

According to Okonkwo and Ekwueme, (2022) Automated Teller Machine is a computer-controlled device that can be instructed to dispense cash and equally provide other services to customers who are identified with a personal identification number (PIN). The introduction of this service has greatly reduced the physical carriage of cash and frequent visits to the banks. With ATM, cash is dispensed at any time of the day and it must not necessarily be located within the banking premises. It could be located even in stores, shopping malls, and fuel stations. This is different from the customary method where customers queue, and sometimes, for a very long period to withdraw cash or transfer funds. The ATM is the most popular e-transaction solution in Nigeria. Its popularity stems from its convenience as it has rendered withdrawing cash, or checking of account balance a lot easier (Okonkwo & Ekwueme, 2022).

However, despite its popularity, the effect of ATM has not been as expected as there is still huge amount of cash in circulation in the economy. Apparently, its introduction has done very little in reducing the amount of cash in the economy. This could be attributable to the fact that most Nigerians use ATM only for cash withdrawal. The vast majority of customers ignore the fact that

ATM machines can perform other functions like fund/cash transfer, mobile phone credit recharge and bills payment. It has been noticed that cash withdrawals and balance inquiry are the most popular applications requested by users in Nigeria. This may be due to absence of education on the part of banks that are expected to properly educate their customers. The absence of merchants has also been cited among the reasons for not utilizing the other functions of ATM. For the fact that ATM machines are mainly used for cash withdrawals, their impact has not gone far enough in turning Nigeria into a cashless economy. ATM has succeeded in making more cash available in the economy since depositors can withdraw cash with ease. To turn Nigeria into a cashless economy, Nigerians need more than just ATM cards; they need credit/debit cards (Okonkwo & Ekwueme, 2022)

Internet Banking

According to Olorunsegun (2010) getting access by customers to their various accounts in addition to wide-ranging information on bank products and services and making use of banks' websites without inconveniencing themselves by sending letters, faxes, original signature, and or telephone confirmation, is what is referred to as Internet banking. In the words of Siyanbola (2013), internet banking involves carrying out banking transactions using the internet (www) by means of electronic tools, for example the computer, without visiting the banking hall. E- Commerce is known to have been facilitated by internet banking and is most frequently used to effect payment. Internet banking like mobile banking equally employs the use of the electronic card infrastructure to execute payment instructions and merchants use it for final settlement of goods and services with their customers over the internet. Some of the most widely used internet banking transactions in Nigeria include settlement of commercial bills as well as purchase of air tickets through the websites of the merchants. It has been noticed that the level of awareness of the saving populace of the benefits of this product is still very low.

This implies that there is still room for improvement if the effectiveness of cashless banking would be upheld as expected (Olaiya & Adeleke, 2019). Internet banking (e-banking) is the use of internet and telecommunication networks to deliver a wide range of value-added products and services to bank customers (Olatinwo, Uwaleke & Ibrahim, 2022) through the use of a system that allows individuals to perform banking activities at home or from their offices or over the internet. Some of these services are offered by traditional banks which also offer online banking; meanwhile some are specifically online only without any physical presence. With online banking in traditional banks, customers could perform most

routine transactions, including account transfers, balance inquiries, bill payments, and stop-payment requests. Some go as far as offering online loan applications. In addition, it has been made possible for customers to access account information at any time of the day, and from anywhere. Internet banking has improved banking efficiency in rendering services to customers.

The Card System

The card system is a unique electronic payment type. The smart cards are plastic devices with embedded integrated circuit being used for settlement of financial obligations. The power of cards lies in their sophistication and acceptability to store and manipulate data, and handles multiple applications on one card securely (Amedu, 2005). Depending on the sophistication, it can be used as a Credit Card, Debit Card and ATMs (Automatic Teller Machine). While the electronic card is gaining popularity in USA and Nigeria, the Spanish financial Institution demonstrated the highest implementation and update of smart cards across Europe (Amedu, 2005). The Smart Card was introduced into the Nigerian market to reduce or eliminate problems of carrying cash about (Amedu, 2005).

It is electronically loaded with cash value and carried about like credit card and stores information on a microchip. The microchip contains a “purse” in which value is hold electronically. In addition, it also contains security programs; these protect transactions between one card user and the other. It can also be transferred directly to a retailer, merchant or other outlet to pay for goods and services, and like cash, transaction between individual without the needs for banks of the other third parties. Also, the system does not require central clearing. It is valued immediately. Also the system allows transfer of one value to the other hence it operates like cash.

Point of Sale (POS) Machine

Point of Sales (POS) machine or terminal is an electronic device used in payment for goods and services. You find it in supermarkets, hotels, filling stations, shops etc. A charge known as Merchant Service Charge (MSC) is charged on all transactions done on POS terminals; this charge is borne by the merchant. The maximum total fee a merchant can be charged for any POS terminal transaction is 0.75% of the transaction value or N1,200.00 cap. Point of Sale refers to the location at which a payment of a card transaction occurs, usually by way of a device such as a credit card terminal or cash register. The industry has endorsed four manufacturers for the supply of Point-of- Sale terminals - PAX, Bitel, Ingenico, and Verifone - with negotiated discounts and local support arrangements. A POS can be purchased from any of these four for as low as N45,000.00 per terminal. However, parties are free to purchase POS terminals from any manufacturer; so far they meet the POS specifications in the Point-of-Sale guidelines.

Economic Liquidity

Economic liquidity is a core factor that reflects the financial market’s operating efficiency. It can effectively enhance pricing efficiency’s information effect and production efficiency’s governance effect, alleviate information asymmetry, reduce transaction costs and market risks, optimize business decisions, improve the capital allocation efficiency of enterprises, and increase corporate value (Li, Wang, Zhou, Wang, & Mardani, 2010). However, problems such as internal and external information asymmetry and management opportunism caused by agency conflicts have become predominant reasons for inhibiting corporate stock liquidity (Chung, Elder, & Kim, 2010). Modern corporate governance theory holds that effective corporate governance can restrain short-term management behaviors and enhance management mechanisms and information transparency, thus improving financial liquidity. On the one hand, a high-quality governance environment can expand corporate financing channels, market activity, and recognition, optimize capital structures, balance stock structures and leverage levels, reduce stock costs and information asymmetry, ease financing constraints, and improve stock liquidity (Ali, Liu & Su, 2016; Niu, Wang, Wen & Li, 2023; Tian, & Shao, 2023). On the other hand, efficient corporate governance can enhance the quality of risk disclosures, accounting information, and corporate earnings, improve internal governance mechanisms, product market competition and innovation ability, sustainable development ability, and comprehensive strength of enterprises, and reduce investment and debt default risks, thus improving stock liquidity (Elshandidy & Neri, 2015

Digital payment is an essential phase in the digital economy era. The deep integration of enterprise total factors and digital technologies can foster the reorganization of production resources and business process reengineering, enhance corporate governance capabilities, corporate value, and internal governance mechanisms, and optimize the corporate governance environment (Wu & Huang, 2022). Notably; this is achieved through the following ways.

First, digital payment system can tackle the problem of financing constraints in corporate governance, create internal and external supervisory mechanisms by reducing information asymmetry, acquire support from external investors, creditors and the government, and promote corporate financing (Wu, Hu, Lin, & Ren, 2022, Zhang, Li, & Xiang, 2023).

Second, digitalization can significantly enhance the quality of internal control of enterprises. Through internal and external cooperation, enterprises can optimize factor allocation, lessen agency problems, strengthen the internal environment, information communication efficiency, and risk prevention capacity, and thus improve the internal control level of enterprises (Feng, Wang Song & Liu, 2022; Guo, Xu, Wang & Li, 2023).

Finally, the digital payment system can effectually improve the information disclosure level. market enrich the information transmission channels through digital technology, improve the ability of information mining and processing, strengthen the internal information disclosure system, and ensure information authenticity, thus enhancing the quality of information disclosure (Wang, Mbanyele & Muchenje, 2022; Nasiri, Ukko, Saunila, Rantala, & Rantanen, 2020).

Theoretical Framework

Developer-Based (Diffusion) Theory

The Developer-based (diffusion) theory was postulated by Rogers (1995) and states that many factors interact to influence the diffusion of an innovation. The four major factors that influence the diffusion process is the innovation itself, how information about the innovation is communicated, time, and the nature of the social system into which the innovation is being introduced (Rogers, 1995). This theory supports how financial innovations influence financial performance. This process relies heavily on human capital. The innovation according to MacKenzie (1996) must be widely adopted in order to self-sustain. MacKenzie (1998) added that within the rate of adoption, there is a point at which an innovation reaches critical mass. In this, diffusion manifests itself in different ways and is highly subject to the type of adopters and innovation-decision process. The criterion for the adopter categorization is innovativeness, defined as the degree to which an individual adopts a new idea.

Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) Theory

The Technology Acceptance Model theory postulated by Davis (1989), states that perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use are the main drivers of technology and these determine an individual's intention to adopt a technology. This theory as adapted from the Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA) by Ajzen and Fishbein (1980) and Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB), developed by Ajzen (1985), which is tailored to the context of technology acceptance and usage supports how cash handling practices influence financial performance. According to Bátiz-Lazo (2018), the intention to use serves as mediator of the actual adoption of technology. To the words of Bátiz-Lazo (2018), the decision to adopt a technology follows the four stages as explained below: Stage one is where the external variables such as individual user beliefs or differences with Information Technology. Their evaluation is reflected in Perceived Usefulness (PU) and Perceived Ease of Use (PeU).

Whereas perceived usefulness is a user perception that using the new system would increase his/her performance in the organization and perceived ease of use is the extent to which using the new system would require minimal effort on a user's behalf (Tilakaratna, 2016). Stage two is attitude which is a consequence of the user's beliefs of using a technology drives the user's attitude towards accepting/rejecting the technology. Stage three is intention where the attitude predicts the desirability of the user using the system and the extent of them using it. Stage four is actual use which is the user's intention to determine how well they would actually use the system. The adoption of technology depends

on personal behaviour and external environment. People perceive that by using technology, they will obtain more benefits without doing much physical and mental effort (Tilakaratna, 2016).

Gefen, Karahanna and Straub (2003) studied a separate and distinct interaction of both the actual e-vendor and with its IT Web site interface is at the heart of online shopping. Previous research has established, accordingly, that online purchase intentions are the product of both consumer assessments of the IT itself-specifically its perceived usefulness and ease-of-use and trust in the e-vendor (Nithin, Jijin & Baiju, 2018). The research showed that consumer trust is as important to online commerce as the widely accepted TAM use-antecedents, perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use. Thus, these variable sets explain a considerable proportion of variance in intended behavior. The study also provided evidence that online trust is built through the belief that the vendor has nothing to gain by cheating, the belief that there are safety mechanisms built into the Web site, and lastly by having a typical interface that is easy to use.

The following are the strengths of the model:

- a. Strong predictive power of consumer's behavioral intention that has been demonstrated with a wide variety of consumer products.
- b. TAM has been effective for explaining many kinds of systems use (i.e. e-learning, learning management, web portals)
- c. More so, TAM is ideally suited to explain the adoption of purely intrinsic or hedonic systems.

METHODOLOGY

The study adopted ex-post facto research design to examine the effect of digital payment instruments on the liquidity of Nigeria economy. The secondary sources of data as used in the study include: Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) Publications. The formulation of the model used in this study was based on theories, an empirical studies, and conceptual analysis of the relationship between digital payment instruments and liquidity of the financial market.

FML = f (ATM, POS, EFT, MP, e-WALLET)

From the above stated model, we adopt the models below in this study

$$FML = \beta_0 + \beta_1 ATM + \beta_2 POS + \beta_3 EFT + \beta_4 MP + \beta_5 e - WALLET + Et \quad (1)$$

Where:

- | | | |
|---------------------|---|--|
| EL | = | Economic liquidity measured as M3/GDP |
| ATM | = | Automated Teller machine |
| POS | = | Point of sale |
| MP | = | Mobile Payment |
| EFT | = | Electronic fund transfer |
| E-WALLET | = | Value of e-wallet transactions |
| Et | = | Error Term |
| β_0 | = | Regression Intercept |
| $\beta_1 - \beta_4$ | = | Coefficient of the Independent variables to the dependent variable |

Data Analysis

The method of data analysis to be used in this study is the multiple linear regressions using ordinary least square method. This approach, which is a quantitative technique, includes tables and the test for the hypotheses formulated by using ordinary least square with software package regression analysis at 5% level of significance. Moreover, in order to undertake a statistical evaluation of our analytical model, so as to determine the reliability of the result obtained and the coefficient of correlation (r) of the regression, the coefficient of determination (r^2), the student T-test and F-test where employed.

Unit Root

Before estimating the electronic payment and national development relationship, this study examined the stationarity status of the data. This test is important to guide against the generation of misleading results. To achieve this objective, two tests i.e. Augmented Dicker-Fuller (ADF) (Dickey & Fuller, 1979) and Philips-Perron (PP) (Phillips & Perron, 1988) tests were employed.

The ADF equation is specified as:

$$\Delta y_t = a + \rho y_{t-1} + \theta_1 \Delta y_{t-1} + \dots + \theta_k \Delta y_{t-k} + \varepsilon_t \quad (2)$$

where y_t is the series, and ε_t the error term. The equation is used to test the null hypothesis: $H_0: \rho = 0$ (unit root) against the alternative hypothesis:

$H_1: \rho < 0$ (series is stationary) The PP test was used as a complement to the ADF test. If the ADF or PP statistic is lower than the critical value at the 1%, 5% or 10%, the H_0 is not rejected. On the other hand, if the statistic is larger than the critical value, the H_1 is accepted.

ARDL Bounds Test to Cointegration

To investigate if there is a long-run relationship between national developments and electronic, the ARDL-bounds test to cointegration technique (Pesaran & Shin, 1999; Pesaran, Shin & Smith, 2001) was used. The method can be applied if the series are I(1) or a combination of I(1) and I(0). The advantages of this technique over the conventional cointegration approaches including those of Engle and Granger (1987), Johansen (1988, 1991), and Johansen and Juselius (1990) have been explained in details in the literature (Abu, 2017, 2019; Abu et al., 2019; Abu & Staniewski, 2019). Some of these advantages include its flexibility for variables to have different optimal lags; using a single reduced form equation to estimate the long-run and the short-run parameters of the model at the same time; and its adequacy in estimating relationships even with finite sample. The ARDL model ($p, k_1, k_2, k_3, k_4, k_5$) is specified as:

$$ELIt = \delta_0 + \sum_{i=1}^p \delta_{1i} ELIt-i + \sum_{i=0}^{k_1} \delta_{2i} k_1 i=0 ATMt-i + \sum_{i=0}^{k_2} \delta_{3i} k_2 i=0 ATMt-i * ATMt-i + \sum_{i=0}^{k_3} \delta_{4i} k_3 i=0 POST-i + \sum_{i=0}^{k_4} \delta_{5i} k_4 i=0 POST-i + \sum_{i=0}^{k_5} \delta_{6i} k_5 i=0 \Delta EFTt-i + \beta_1 EFTt-1 + \beta_2 ATMt-1 + \beta_3 ATMt-1 * e-walletRt-1 + \beta_4 MPt-1 + \beta_5 MPt-1 + \beta_6 MPt-1 + \mu \quad (3)$$

The bounds test is conducted by testing the null hypothesis of no cointegration (H_0) against the alternative hypothesis (H_1) using the following equations: $H_0: \beta_1 = \beta_2 = \beta_3 = \beta_4 = \beta_5 = 0$, and $H_1: \beta_1 \neq \beta_2 \neq \beta_3 \neq \beta_4 \neq 0$

The computed F-statistic (i.e. Wald test) was used to test the joint significance of the coefficients, and its value compared with the lower and upper critical bounds values. If the F-statistic is higher than the upper critical bound, the H_0 is not accepted. However, if the F-statistic is less than the lower bound, the H_0 is not rejected. But if the F-statistic falls between the upper and lower bounds, then the decision will be inconclusive. If cointegration is found among the variables, both the long-run and the short-run coefficients would be estimated using the following models:

$$ELt = \theta_0 + \theta_1 ATMt + \theta_2 ATMt * ATMt + \theta_3 POST + \theta_4 EFTt + \theta_5 MPt + \mu t \quad (4) \text{ and,}$$

$$ELt = \beta_0 + \sum_{i=0}^p \beta_{1i} p i=0 ELt-i + \sum_{i=0}^{k_1} \beta_{2i} k_1 i=0 ATMt-i + \sum_{i=0}^{k_2} \beta_{3i} k_2 i=0 ATMt-i * ATMt-i + \sum_{i=0}^{k_3} \beta_{4i} k_3 i=0 POST-i + \sum_{i=0}^{k_4} \beta_{5i} k_4 i=0 EFTt-i + \sum_{i=0}^{k_5} \beta_{6i} k_5 i=0 w-wallett-i + \psi_1 ECTt-1 + \mu \quad (4)$$

$ECTt-1$ is the error correction term which is lagged by one period, and its coefficient (ψ_1) is the speed of adjustment that is required to restore long-run equilibrium in the event of any deviation/shock. The Akaike Information Criterion (AIC) was employed in selecting optimal lags for the variables. The AIC was used due to its superiority over other lag selection criteria even in small samples (Liew, 2004; Tang & Lean, 2007a).

Tests of Significance

The study employed use of One – Way E-view to test whether there were significant statistical differences among the means of the four independent variables.

Prior Expectation of the Result

The a-priori expectation of the variables proposes that an increase in the explanatory variables lead to increase in the dependent variables. Therefore it can be mathematical stated as follows: - $a_1, a_2, a_3, a_4, a_5 < 0$.

ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Table 1: ADF Unit Root Test

Variable	ADF Statistic	MacKinnon 1%	@ 5%	10%	Order of integration
EL	- 2.880883	-4.121990	-3.144920	-2.713751	I(0)
ATM	6.658008	-4.121990	-3.144920	-2.713751	I(1)
E-WALLET	4.658008	-4.121990	-3.144920	-2.713751	I(1)
MP	-9.318257	-4.004425	-3.098896	-2.690439	I(1)
POS	-5.884645	-4.004425	-3.098896	-2.690439	I(1)
EFT	-6.033455	-4.121990	-3.144920	-2.713751	I(1)

Source: Computed from E-View 9.0

In structural break analysis in this study, each variable was examined using the Dickey-Fuller breakpoint (ADF-BP) unit root test and Bai-Peron multiple breakpoints test was also applied to the variables. This was necessary because the conventional Dickey-Fuller-type unit root test due to their low power, do not perform well in the face of structural break(s) in the series; and as such they fail to reject the unit root null hypothesis when it is incorrect (Brooks, 2014). Therefore, the variables are stationary at first difference. On the other hand, INF does not have a unit root or it is stationary at level [i.e. I(0)]. The mixture of [I(0)] and [I(1)] provides the justification for using an ARDL-bounds test to cointegration.

Table 4.4 Results of Bounds Test to Cointegration

F-Bounds Test		Null Hypothesis: No levels relationship			
Test Statistic	Value	Signif.	I(0)	I(1)	
F-statistic k	8.311067 2	10%	2.63	3.35	
		5%	3.1	3.87	
		2.5%	3.55	4.38	
		1%	4.13	5	
		Asymptotic: n=1000			
Actual Sample Size	12	10%	2.845	3.623	
		5%	3.478	4.335	
		1%	4.948	6.028	
		Finite Sample: n=35			
		10%	2.915	3.695	
		5%	3.538	4.428	
		1%	5.155	6.265	

Source: Computed from E-View 9.0

The F-Bounds cointegration test was conducted to determine the existence or non-existence of long-run relationship among the variables of study. The results of the test as presented in Table 4.4 uncover the existence of long-run relationship between digital payment instruments and economic liquidity.

Table 3: ARDL Short Run Results

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.*
EL (-1)	-0.296330	0.186304	-1.590570	0.1266
ATM	-0.011260	0.012615	-0.892571	0.3822
E-WALLET	0.085686	0.364248	0.235241	0.8163
MP (-1)	0.055315	0.382874	0.144474	0.8865
POS	-0.847832	0.690708	-1.227484	0.2332
POS (-1)	-0.499810	0.455661	-1.096889	0.2851
POS (-2)	0.480987	0.353018	1.362500	0.1875
EFT	0.454780	0.337665	1.346839	0.1924
EFT (-1)	-0.189470	0.409105	-0.463134	0.6480
EFT (-2)	-0.618803	0.614985	-1.006209	0.3258
C	69.93706	15.63626	4.472748	0.0002
R-squared	0.917701	Mean dependent var		53.04844
Adjusted R-squared	0.868463	S.D. dependent var		4.745893
S.E. of regression	4.327715	Akaike info criterion		6.034243
Sum squared resid	393.3115	Schwarz criterion		6.538090
Log likelihood	-85.54789	Hannan-Quinn criter.		6.201254
F-statistic	28.30617	Durbin-Watson stat		2.033353
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000			

Source: Computed from E-View 9.0

The results of the ARDL short-run and Error Correction Model (ECM) for the five comparative variables in this study are presented in Table 4. The short-run estimates indicate that 91.7 percent of the variance in liquidity of Nigeria economy was explained by changes in digital payment instruments. The F-statistic for the regression model is 28.30617, and the P-value is 0.000000, which indicates that the model fits the data well overall. The Durbin Watson Statistic was calculated to be 2.033353 which suggested that there were some degree of temporal dependency in the level series. The study found that automated teller machine, point of sales, electronic fund transfer have negative effect on liquidity of the economy while e-wallet and mobile payment have positive effect on the liquidity of the economy. This enables us to examine the results using the ARDL long run model.

Table 4: ARDL Long Run Form and Bounds Test

Conditional Error Correction Regression				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	69.93706	15.63626	4.472748	0.0002
EL (-1)*	-1.296330	0.186304	-6.958134	0.0000
ATM **	0.011260	0.012615	0.892571	0.3822
E-WALLET (-1)	0.030371	0.234769	0.129364	0.8983
MP (-1)	-0.866655	0.552117	-1.569694	0.1314
POS (-1)	1.263054	0.506366	2.494348	0.0210
D(ATM)	0.085686	0.364248	0.235241	0.8163
D(E-WALLET)	-0.847832	0.690708	-1.227484	0.2332
D(MP(-1))	-0.480987	0.353018	-1.362500	0.1875
D(POS)	0.454780	0.337665	1.346839	0.1924
D(EFT (-1))	-0.618803	0.614985	-1.006209	0.3258

Source: E-view 12.0

The results of the long -run model indicates that mobile payment has a positive and significant effect on economic liquidity, a 1 unit increase in mobile payment leads to approximately 0.8% decrease in economic liquidity at 1% level. Electronic fund transfer has a negative and significant effect on economic

liquidity, a 1 unit increase in mobile payment leads to approximately 0.86% decreases in economic liquidity at 1% level. Automated teller machine has a positive and no significant effect on economic liquidity, a 1 unit increase in Automated teller machine leads to approximately 0.08% increase in economic liquidity at 1% level with standard error less than 1.0 while point of sales has a negative and significant effect on economic liquidity, a 1 unit decrease in point of sales leads to approximately 0.45% increase crease in economic liquidity at 1% level with standard error less than 1.0.

Table 4.7 ARDL Error Correction Regression

Case 2: Restricted Constant and No Trend				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
D(EL(-1))	-1.713937	0.188818	-9.077179	0.0003
D(EL(-2))	-1.404067	0.180397	-7.783189	0.0006
D(POS)	0.300356	0.087525	3.431655	0.0186
CointEq(-1)*	-0.782315	0.107266	-7.293204	0.0008
R-squared	0.916994	Mean dependent var		0.998333
Adjusted R-squared	0.885867	S.D. dependent var		4.622616
S.E. of regression	1.561687	Akaike info criterion		3.990612
Sum squared resid	19.51092	Schwarz criterion		4.152247
Log likelihood	-19.94367	Hannan-Quinn criter.		3.930768
Durbin-Watson stat	2.534619			

Source: Computed from E-View 9.0

The error correction term (ECT) of the model is negative (-0.782315) and statistically significant which implies that the short-run disturbance to the short-run equilibrium is corrected at a rate of about 78 percent per annum to bring about long-run equilibrium. Just like in the long-run, the variables have positive effect on the dependent variable.

The positive effect of the variables confirms the expectations of the study. The findings is in line with the findings of Peter (2015) that ease of use, accessibility and security are factors that produce satisfaction to customers and encourage the usage or adopted of internet banking which has a positive influence that is statistically significant, Udobi-owoloja *et al.*, (2020) that electronic banking platform such as USSD and POS also recorded a greater decrease of usage and together with other platform aided banking transaction and international transfers on line and therefore all contributed positively to the profitability of banking firms in Nigeria, Amin, (2016) that internet banking service quality has a positive relationship with e-commerce satisfaction and e-loyalty. This result or findings is in consistence with findings of Herington and Weaven (2009) and Sohail and Shaikh (2008) stated that efficiency of website is the most influencing factor in user’s evaluation of internet banking service quality and that online banking customers are focusing more on speed and how to complete their banking transaction accurately and in real time, Ho and Lin (2010) , Mukherjee (2003) that opportunistic behavior tend to have a critical negative impact or effect on trust and that regulatory control plays a critical or significant role in controlling opportunistic behavior. Reputation was found to be a critical component of trust and is most influence by resulting outcomes. Lumpkin and Schich (2020) that the effective re-bundling and unbundling of retail banking services and product are provided separately in some cases. In other cases, they are provided in re-bundled forms together with other services and additional new services, delivered in a manner that is more convenient to customers. The negative findings of the variables is not supported by the findings of Obiekwe and Anyanwaokoro (2017) that Automated Teller Machine (ATM) and Mobile Phone payment have a significant effect on the profitability of commercial banks in Nigeria, Hussein and Elyjoy (2018) adopted a cross-sectional research design. The population of the study comprised of 56 employees of the commercial banks.

CONCLUSION

This study looked at the effect of digital payment instruments and economic liquidity in Nigeria using time series data sourced from Central Bank of Nigeria Statistical Bulletin and World Bank Data Base.

Autoregressive Distribution Lag was used as data analysis method. The study found that 91.7 percent of the variance in liquidity of Nigeria economy was explained by changes in digital payment instruments. The F-statistic for the regression model is 28.30617, and the P-value is 0.000000, this indicted that the model fits the data well overall. The Durbin Watson Statistic was found to be 2.033353 which suggested that there were some degree of temporal dependency in the level series. The study found that automated teller machine, point of sales, electronic fund transfer have negative effect on liquidity of the economy while e-wallet and mobile payment have positive effect on the liquidity of the economy. This enables us to examine the results using the ARDL long run model. From the findings, we conclude that digital payment instrument determine the liquidity of Nigeria economy.

RECOMMENDATIONS

- i. Government should subsidize the purchase of point of sale machines such that most traders, vendors and business people are able and willing to own one. There is the need for more investment to be made in internet network provision by the government of Nigeria and to also make favourable policies that will entice more private sector-driven investment in the digital payment instrument.
- ii. More neo-banks should be licensed and encouraged to drive the cashless policy which will promote healthy competition with the commercial banks. The payment system is an operational network governed by laws, rules and standards that links bank accounts and provides the functionality of monetary exchange using the digital payment instruments.
- iii. Banks should constantly upgrade hardware and software whenever a new feature for enhancing security becomes available, implementation of the e-payment systems has much to do with internet connectivity and mobile banking, and efforts should be made to design or improve the internet security framework to check online fraud.
- iv. There should be adequate legislation on all aspects of the operations of the e-banking and cashless system so that both the operators of the system and the public can be adequately protected; government should reduce the charges for the use of electronic means of transactions to encourage people to use them more often.
- v. The study thus recommended the improvement of the technological base of the country and policy measures to encourage the efficient performance of the banking sector as well as regulation and control of the banking activities and banks management should create awareness to inform the public about the benefits derived on the e-banking service products.

REFERENCES

- Abu, N. (2017). Does Okun's law exist in Nigeria? Evidence from ARDL bounds testing approach. *Contemporary Economics*, 11(2), 131-144
- Abu, N. (2019). Inflation and unemployment trade-off: A re-examination of the Phillips curve and its stability in Nigeria. *Contemporary Economics*, 13(1), 21-34.
- Abu, N., & Staniewski, M. W. (2019). Determinants of corruption in Nigeria: Evidence from various estimation techniques. *Economic Research-Ekonomska Istraživanja*, 32(1), 3052-3076
- Aduda, J. & Kingoo, F. (2018). A contingency model of leadership effectiveness, *Advances in experimental social psychology*, 1 (12), 149-190.
- Ai Y, Sun G, Kong T. (2022). Digital finance and stock price crash risk. *International Review of Economics & Finance*. 2023; 88:607–19.
- Ajzen, I., & Fishbein, M. (1980). *Understanding attitudes and predicting social behavior*. Englewood Cliffs, NJ: Prentice-Hall.
- Ali S, Liu B & Su JJ (2016).. What determines stock liquidity in Australia? *Applied Economics*. 2016; 48 (35):3329–3344.
- Amihud Y,& Mendelson H. (1998). Liquidity, volatility, and exchange automation. *Journal of Accounting, Auditing and Finance*. 1988; 3(4):369–95.

- Amin, E., Onyeukwu, S., & Osuagwu, J. (2018). Effects of financing on the performance of small and medium enterprises (SMEs). *International Journal of Management*, 2 (10), 1-9.
- Amin, M. (2016). Internet banking service quality and its implications on e-customers satisfaction and e-customer loyalty. *International Journal of Bank Marketing*, 34(3), 280-306.
- An J, Ding W, & Lin C.(2023). ChatGPT: tackle the growing carbon footprint of generative AI. *Nature*. 615 (7953):586-.
- An J, Rau R. (2021). Finance, technology and disruption. *The European Journal of Finance*. 27(4-5):334-45.
- Baiyere A, Salmela H, Tapanainen T. (2020). Digital transformation and the new logics of business process management. *European journal of information systems*, 29(3):238-59.
- Bátiz-Lazo B. (2018). *Cash and dash: How ATMs and computers changed banking*. Oxford University Press.
- Bennett B, Stulz R, & Wang Z (2020). Does the stock market make firms more productive? *Journal of Financial Economics*, 136(2):281-306.
- Chen W, Zhang L, Jiang P, Meng F, Sun Q (2022). Can digital transformation improve the information environment of the capital market? Evidence from the analysts' prediction behaviour. *Accounting & Finance*, 62(2):2543-78.
- Chung KH, Elder J, & Kim J-C. (2010) Corporate governance and liquidity. *Journal of financial and quantitative analysis*, 45(2):265-91.
- Davis, F.D. (1986). A Technology Acceptance Model for Empirically Testing New End-user information Systems: Theory and Results. Doctoral Dissertation, MIT Sloan School of Management, Cambridge, MA.
- Davis, F.D. (1989). Perceived Usefulness, Perceived Ease Of Use, And User Acceptance. *MIS Quarterly*, 13(3), 319- 340.
- Elshandidy T, Neri L. Corporate governance, risk disclosure practices, and market liquidity: Comparative evidence from the UK and Italy. *Corporate Governance: An International Review*,23(4):331-56.
- Engle, R. F., & Granger, C. J. (1987). Cointegration and error-correction - Representation, estimation and testing. *Econometrica*, 55(2), 251-278
- Feng H, Wang F, Song G, Liu L (2022). Digital transformation on enterprise green innovation: Effect and transmission mechanism. *International journal of environmental research and public health*, 19 (17),1-22.
- Gefen, D., Karahanna, E. & Straub, D.W. (2003) Trust and TAM in Online Shopping: An Integrated Model. *MIS quarterly*, 27, 51-90.
- Gopalan R, Kadan O, & Pevzner M. (2022). Asset liquidity and stock liquidity. *Journal of Financial and Quantitative Analysis*. 2012; 47(2):333-64.
- Guo L, Xu L, Wang J, Li J. (2023). Digital transformation and financing constraints of SMEs: evidence from China. *Asia-Pacific Journal of Accounting & Economics*, 1-21. <https://doi.org/10.1080/16081625.2023.2257235>
- Johansen, S. (1988). Statistical analysis of cointegration vectors. *Journal of Economic Dynamics and Control*, 12(2-3), 231-254.
- Johansen, S. (1991). Estimation and hypothesis testing of cointegration vectors in Gaussian vector autoregressive models. *Econometrica*, 59(6), 1551-1580.
- Johansen, S., & Juselius, K. (1990). Maximum likelihood estimation and inference on cointegration - With applications to the demand for money. *Oxford Bulletin of Economics and Statistics*, 52(2), 169-210
- Lei Q, Lin, B., & Wei M. (2013). Types of agency cost, corporate governance and liquidity. *Journal of Accounting and Public Policy*, 32(3), 147-172.

- Li C, Wang Y, Zhou Z, Wang Z, & Mardani A (2010). Digital finance and enterprise financing constraints: Structural characteristics and mechanism identification. *Journal of Business Research*, 165:114074.
- Lumpkin, S. & Schich, S. (2020). Banks, digital initiatives and the financial safety net theory and analytical framework. *Journal of Economics Science Research*, 3(1), 24-46.
- MacKenzie, I. S. and Oniszczak, A., (1998). A comparison of three selection techniques for touchpads, Proceedings of the ACM SIGCHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems - CHI '98, (New York: ACM, 1998), 336-343.
- Mukherjee, A. & Nath, P. (2003). A Model of trust on online relationship banking. *International Journal of Bank Marketing*, 5-15.
- Nasiri M, Ukko J, Saunila M, Rantala T, & Rantanen H. (2020). Digital-related capabilities and financial performance: the mediating effect of performance measurement systems. *Technology Analysis & Strategic Management*, 32(12),1393–406.
- Nithin, M., Jijin, P., & Baiju, P. (2018). Has Demonetisation Pushed Digitalisation in India? Some Counter Evidences. *Journal of Business Thought*, 9, 58-69
- Niu Y, Wang S, Wen W, & Li S. (2023). Does digital transformation speed up dynamic capital structure adjustment? Evidence from China. *Pacific-Basin Finance Journal*. 79:102016. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pacfin.2023.102016>.
- Okonkwo, A. A., & Ekwueme, C. M., (2022). E-Payment and Performance of Deposit Money Banks in Nigeria. *Research Journal of Management Practice*, 2(3), 23-24
- Olaiya, A. C. & Adeleke, K. O. (2019). Electronic banking and profitability of deposit money banks in Nigeria. *Journal of Association of Professional Bankers in Education*, 5(1), 129-153.
- Olatinwo, A. I., Uwaleke, U., & Ibrahim, U. A., (2022), Impact of Financial Services on Financial Performance of Commercial Banks in Nigeria. *International Journal of Economics and Management Systems*, 7, 300-307.
- Oniore, J. O. & Okoli, U. V. (2019). Impact of electronic banking on the performance of money deposit banks in Nigeria. *Noble International Journal of Economics and Financial Research*, 4(9), 83-90.
- Osang, F. B. (2017). E-Banking: Evaluating electronic payment channels in Southern Nigeria. *NOUN Journal of Physical and Life Sciences*, 1, 135-157.
- Osuigwe, O. C., (2022). Financial innovation and economic growth in Nigeria. *International Journal of Innovative Social Science & Humanities Research* 10(2), 36-51.
- Pesaran, H. M., & Shin, Y. (1999). Autoregressive distributed lag modelling approach to cointegration analysis. In: Storm, S. Editor. *econometrics and economic theory in the 20th century; The Ragnar Frisch centennial symposium*. Cambridge University Press, (chapter 11).
- Pesaran, M. H., Shin, Y., & Smith R. J. (2001). Bounds testing approaches to the analysis of level relationships. *Journal of Applied Econometrics*, 16, 289- 326.
- Peter, A. A.O. (2015). Factors affecting the adoption of internet banking in Nigeria
- Phillips, P. C., & Perron, P. (1988). Testing for a unit root in time series regression. *Biometrika*, 75(2), 335-346.
- Prommin P, Jumreornvong S, Jiraporn P. (2014). The effect of corporate governance on stock liquidity: The case of Thailand. *International Review of Economics & Finance*, 32:132–142.
- Quah H, Haman J, Naidu D. (2021). The effect of stock liquidity on investment efficiency under financing constraints and asymmetric information: Evidence from the United States. *Accounting & Finance*, 61:2109–50.
- Rogers (1995) *Diffusion of Innovations*. 5th Edition, Free Press, New York.
- Schoenfeld J. (2017). The effect of voluntary disclosure on stock liquidity: New evidence from index funds. *Journal of Accounting and Economics*. 2017; 63(1):51–74.
- Tian J, & Shao B. (2023). Financing constraints and information asymmetry of SMEs—The development of digital finance and financial risks of enterprises. *Journal of the Knowledge Economy*, 1–21.

- Udeghe, M. & Hanzace, K. (2018). Accounting information and managerial work, *Accounting, Organizations and Society*, 35(3), 301-315.
- Udobi-owaloja, P. I., Akhigbe, B. E., Ubi, A. E., Gbajumo-sheriff, M. A. & Umoru, B. (2020). Digital banking and bank profitability in Nigeria. *Nigeria Journal of Management Studies*, 20(2), 24-34.
- Wang F, Mbanye W, & Muchenje L (2022). Economic policy uncertainty and stock liquidity: The mitigating effect of information disclosure. *Research in International Business and Finance*, 59:101553. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ribaf.2021.101553>.
- Wu F, Hu H, Lin H, Ren X. Enterprise digital transformation and capital market performance: Empirical evidence from stock liquidity. *Management World*, 37(7), 130–44.
- Wu Y, & Huang S (2022). The effects of digital finance and financial constraint on financial performance: Firmlevel evidence from China's new energy enterprises. *Energy Economics*, 112:106158. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eneco.2022.106158>.
- Zayyanu, M., Umar, A. I., & Taiwo, A. M., (2022). Effect of Payment System Innovations on the Financial Performance of Commercial Banks in Nigeria. *Journal of Service Science and Management*, 15, 35-53
- Zhang H, Ye J, Wei F, Kashif R, Cao C (2023). Monetary policy adjustment, corporate investment, and stock liquidity empirical evidence from Chinese stock market. *Emerging Markets Finance and Trade*, 55(13):3023–38.
- Zhang X, Li J, & Xiang D, (2023) Worthington AC. Digitalization, financial inclusion, and small and medium-sized enterprise financing: Evidence from China. *Economic Modelling*. 2023; 126:106410. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.econmod.2023.106410>.